

Tourist taxes for Public Realm Conservation in Bath: A Stakeholder Analysis

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Abstract

Tourist taxes have been used at heritage sites to maintain the symbiotic relationship between tourism and heritage. However, local authorities in the UK do not have the power to directly implement tourist taxes, leading to political debate. Bath is one of the UK cities interested in the use of tourist taxes for conservation and improving its public realm. This research seeks to present a systematic overview of the problem situation and stakeholder analysis, concluding with their mapping within a power-interest matrix. It was found that the relationship between Bath local authority and lobbying parties, businesses, tourists, and residents already has a strong basis for continued collaboration. However, the one-sided relationship between the government and local authorities means that continued lobbying for tourist taxes will need to continue, or alternative methods to implementing tourist taxes are needed. Despite the challenges, Bath demonstrates examples of beneficial stakeholder collaboration that should be continued to be built on.

Keywords: tourist tax; public realm conservation; cultural heritage management; urban heritage; stakeholder analysis; sustainable tourism; heritage policy

1 Introduction

The World Heritage (WH) List was established during the 1972 General Conference of United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO), listing cultural and natural assets known as World Heritage Sites (WHS). This is established to protect their non-renewable and irreplaceable outstanding universal value (OUV). As these sites are given international renown for their heritage or natural merit, they often receive more tourist visits than non-listed areas, with some positive contributions to their local economies and national imagesⁱ, but also detrimental effects such as overtourism which contribute to the wear and tear of the historic environment.

Heritage tourism is particularly important to the United Kingdom (UK) economy, including visits to WHS. In the UK, day visits alone generated a total visitor spend of £11.5 billion in 2023, while 57% of international tourists surveyed in the same year strongly associate the national heritage of the UK with its tourist economyⁱⁱ. As a result, philosophical issues may occur when heritage tourism brings detrimental effects to local conservation needs. One of the ways the historic built environment could be protected is through well-managed tourism, which includes means such as taxing tourists. Tourism tax has been an established method for regulating tourism and ensuring tourists contribute to the site they visit. WHS globally such as Venice have been charging tourist taxes for reinvestment into their destinationsⁱⁱⁱ.

The double-inscribed UNESCO WHS of Bath has been a popular tourist destination, holding a high tourist-resident ratio. The Bath and Northeast Somerset (BANES) council has ambitions to consider visitor taxation to enhance its OUV, but requires Parliament authorization which so far has been unsuccessful^{iv}. Conflicting resident opinions point to a lack of consensus over tourist tax, where they interrupt public spaces and deter residents from the city centre, yet also contribute to local income^v. However, these opinions are highly anecdotal and reflect only a small part of a wider problem which requires objective examination: how may the BANES council address the tourist tax dilemma which might support its WHS status?

Heritage tourism in the UK is highly relevant in both practice and research. Lobbying for tourist taxes is a live ongoing political topic in English governance, while ongoing research examines the effects of tourist taxes and stakeholders in heritage management^{vi}. The complexity of heritage tourism and conservation is similarly reflected in academic literature. There is an abundance of debate surrounding the conflicting needs of heritage tourism and conservation of WHS, in addition to research on governance and residents with the aim of reconciling complex differences, demonstrating the active nature of the problem.

Existing case studies of stakeholders in heritage sites are highly contextual and are limited in generalisability, requiring further research in cross-comparison. This work makes an academic contribution by creating a stakeholder analysis of WHS complexity in a developed country which can be used in future cross-comparison research. Although the limited duration available disallows extensive data triangulation, it may be combined with mixed-methodology approaches such as those proposed by Berta, Bottero and Ferretti (2018). This research also makes an academic contribution to the academic field of tourist tax implementation in WHS to enhance its OUV, which currently has only one article identifying resident perceptions of tourist taxes^{vii}.

The research primarily benefits local planning authorities in England who face similar issues of heritage tourism such that the analysis may be similarly carried out and applied to their own situation. Bath is one of the many historic cities in the UK which face similar challenges brought

by heritage tourism, and stakeholder analysis is a relatively accessible methodology that can be carried out as the first step to problem demarcation and stakeholder identification.

The article is structured in four sections with references. The following section identifies existing literature on stakeholder analysis in heritage and tourist taxes for conservation. Section 3 explains the methodology of stakeholder analysis used as proposed by Enserink et al. (2022), the problem context, data collected, and limitations. Section 4 presents the findings of the methodology, including all problem demarcation and stakeholder analysis diagrams, and associated assumptions and implications. Section 5 concludes the paper and provides suggestions for further research.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Impact of tourism on heritage

Detrimental impacts on the OUV of WHS trigger enabling legislation to see through both preservation and preservation central to WH management UNESCO, 'Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage', 1972. This creates a legal framework restricting development and subsequently tourism^{viii}. At the same time, WHS inscriptions have been seen as a factor in attracting tourist flow to the sites. Buckley (2018) argues that WHS and tourism share a reciprocal, but asymmetrical relationship – WH management agencies lack cash flow to maintain assets holding OUV, while tourism enterprises want preferential access to generate profit.

The site-tourism relationship however can sometimes be misaligned. In examining stakeholder issues in the prospective WHS listing of Masouleh in Iran, Seyfi, Michael Hall and Fagnoni (2019) found that divergent opinions and a top-down dynamic between residents and authorities create an obstacle, despite the willingness of residents to participate in heritage tourism development^{ix}. Duval and Smith (2013) found that ineffective tourism and conservation management has risked the preservation of vulnerable rock art heritage at South Africa's uKhahlamba-Drakensberg WHS^x. However, collaboration is not a general solution to stakeholder conflict in heritage. In preserving the UNESCO biosphere reserve at Spreewald, Germany, a general tourism levy was considered but not accepted out of concerns of artificial preservation and unequal benefits. Due to failed past attempts of collaboration, trust has been severely eroded^{xi}. These case studies demonstrate the complex relationship between heritage management, tourism, and residents at historic sites around the world that require the establishment of trust and reciprocity over time.

2.2 Stakeholder analysis for decision making

Stakeholder analysis has been used as one of the methodologies supporting decision-making in heritage and conservation in academic literature. Territorial planning has been recognized since the 70s as belonging to wicked problem situations^{xii}. To address wicked problems, the discipline of operational research (OR) uses models to aid decision-making where quantitative approaches are insufficient, especially problem structuring methods (PSMs)^{xiii}.

PSMs, or "soft OR" or "soft systems" methods, were introduced by Rosenhead (1989) to describe methods focusing on the structuring of a problem situation, which includes stakeholder analysis that encourage multi-perspective understanding and facilitate information synthesis^{xiv}. Myers, Smith and Ostergren (2016) incorporates stakeholder theory in heritage management, acknowledging that the legal protection of heritage sites involves multiple stakeholders, and notes that critical stakeholders are connected or associated with the site^{xv}.

Adaptive reuse is one of the fields in heritage adopting three main categories of evaluation frameworks for decision making, as identified by Bottero et al (2022), and various methods are applied across a range of scenarios^{xvi}. These methods are often participatory^{xvii} or offer a cyclical process of evaluation^{xviii}. The evaluation of adopting Industry 5.0 principles in historical bridge conservation also used stakeholder analysis to identify key stakeholders who may play a significant role^{xix}.

A literature review of method combinations for multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) recognizes the relevancy of stakeholder analysis, as it works to recognize actors and their objectives^{xx}. Stakeholder analysis is easy to use and systematic if done properly but may lack academic rigor and little initial knowledge of stakeholders. As an OR research method, it also faces the challenge of limited evidence and evaluation of impact^{xxi}. Some studies used experts to represent stakeholders as part of the decision-making process^{xxii}. However, as stakeholders were not directly consulted, there is a possibility that certain concerns were not accounted for.

2.3 Power dynamics in stakeholder analysis

In addition to facilitating decision making, power dynamics can be identified through stakeholder analysis methods. Drawing on the original intention of OR, Jackson (2004) proposed the concept of 'enhanced OR', where rational methods are used to solve wicked problems for wider public benefit. This necessitates stakeholder involvement in decision-making, transparent analysis, and the consideration of groups affected by power dynamics involved^{xxiii}.

Power dynamics exist across a range of problem situations in literature. Reed et al. (2009) applied stakeholder analysis in natural resources management to understand power dynamics and introduce transparency to decision-making^{xxiv}. Stakeholder impact analysis also highlights that powerless but interested stakeholders influence which adaptive reuse proposal may be preferred^{xxv}, while Ferretti (2021) used the power-interest grid to make explicit existing power dynamics. It directs attention to actors who are interested but lack power to create change. In a case study of the African American community, the matrix was interpreted to recommend universally beneficial policies^{xxvi}. However, this may not necessarily be applicable in real life nor in a heritage setting, so recommendations created require further verification and testing.

In examining forest management, Brodrechtova (2024) used the actor-centred power (ACP) approach to find actors with decisive power. In general, power may be approached based on the relational power between actors or agent power resources, institutions, and discourse. In the ACP framework proposed by Krott et al. (2014), power is defined as social relationship where an actor affects the behaviour of another without expressing their intention or from power resources^{xxvii}. These highlight the significance of resources held in relation to actor influence and power.

Among these power dynamics, it may be possible to find common ground. Reed et al. (2009) finds that stakeholder analysis may enable the appreciation of different views among stakeholders to seek new ways of working together. The notion of achieving consensus has been noted in the field of heritage conservation, such as that of the *Burra Charter*^{xxviii}. However, Aas, Ladkin and Fletcher (2005) identify that collaboration alone neglects the constraint from power and resource distribution^{xxix}. Therefore, in heritage tourism collaboration, understanding power and resource distribution helps identify obstacles to achieving consensus as intended.

2.4 Types of tourist taxes

Tourist taxes have been established in European countries since early 20C. Being an economic tool, they remain an item of academic and political interest. Candela and Figini

(2012) identified three types of tourist taxes: fixed taxes, taxes proportional to the length of stay, and a paid sum proportional to vacation price such as value-added tax (VAT)^{xxx}. They aim to redress balance of unpriced amenities, including historic buildings, and the maintenance of public goods. There is a range of tourist taxes employed at destinations internationally. Most large tourist cities charge accommodation taxes which are easy to manage, resulting in limited compliance costs^{xxxi}. The *Taxe de Sejour* has been applied in France since 1910 to improve tourism. Catalonia employs accommodation taxes, while Venice charges accommodation taxes to reduce footfall damage to its built heritage, and trialled arrivals taxes in 2024^{xxxii}. However, not all these tourism tax models are necessarily applicable to the city of Bath, which has its own unique geography and no fixed entry points^{xxxiii}. Predicted impacts of tourist taxes may not be easily generalised from existing practices, and long-term effects of recent taxes have yet to be understood^{xxxiv}.

Nevertheless, the impact of tourist taxes has been explored in literature. Tourism demand in Italian destinations do not seem to be sensitive to price increases^{xxxv}. The Manchester bed tax has had no significant effect on hotel performance, showing promise for being a powerful income tool with little industrial impact^{xxxvi}. However, tourist taxes remain a controversial economic tool. They may risk introducing tax avoidance practices and face opposition from the tourism industry^{xxxvii} such as underreporting^{xxxviii}.

3 Materials and Methods

3.1 Overview

The methodology is carried out in two main parts (Figure 1). The first part, systems analysis, maps the problem system with an open and empirical working method^{xxxix}. To achieve a solution from a heritage conservation perspective, the problem situation will be constructed accordingly to fulfil the needs of public realm conservation.

Figure 1. Methodology flowchart showing sequence of analyses ((Enserink et al., 2022).

The second part identifies key actors linked to the problem decision arena^{xl}. Public policies are generated within networks where multiple actors are interrelated, with their behaviour explained by actor perceptions, values, and resources. Stakeholder analysis identifies individuals likely to be affected by proposed policy^{xli}. It works to find out interested and powerful parties, how actors interact, and how they may work together better to affect change through the explanation of networks, perceptions, values, and resources identified^{xlii}.

The methodology is carried out in the form of a case study, examining stakeholder relationships in implementing tourist taxes for public realm conservation in the city of Bath. However, the

case presented is limited from restricted time available for multiple sources of data. The secondary data collected may be subject to biases that require further research.

3.2 Problem context

The City of Bath is double inscribed as a UNESCO WHS and as one of the Great Spa Towns of Europe. Its urban planning exemplifies the 18C philosophy of integrating cities in picturesque landscapes, which forms part of its listing criterion^{xliii}. The grand spaces of Georgian Bath were the product of strong management and economic investment, including the strict control of vehicular access and removal of street clutter. Fine pennant stone was laid in key thoroughfares, with its streetscape further enhanced by boundary markers such as wrought iron railings and overthrows^{xliv}. Its Georgian town planning, public realm design, and influence on subsequent developments contributes to its historic significance^{xlv}. However, it has deteriorated over time, with under-investment and poor management causing cluttered and incoherent public spaces. The council aims to develop a long-term strategy requiring significant investment across a range of projects ^{xlvi}.

Developing sustainable tourism to protect Bath's OUV has been considered^{xlvii}. Tourism has been recognized as contributing to the deterioration of the public realm. It was noted that the high volume of day trippers has been detrimental^{xlviii}. The council has expressed interest in identifying value conflicts and seek funding opportunities for sustainable tourism^{xlix}. However, local authorities in the UK do not have the devolved powers to implement tourist taxes, so the council is continuing to explore possibilities, having achieved unanimous agreement on the principle of establishing a tourist tax in Bath^l.

3.3 Means-ends diagram for problem demarcation

The means-ends analysis identifies the problem with a verb sentence expressing the desired situation (end). Consequent posing of the question 'Why is the end worth striving for?' results in a means-ends network. Additional conditions are identified per end. Arrows denote a casual relationship and always point upwards, and each end has none or more than one ingoing arrow for simplicity. The focal objective is selected from the diagram to choose the level for analysis. However, it cannot be one of the lowest means-ends^{li}.

3.4 Objectives tree

After determining the focal objective for the means-ends diagram, the objective tree defines an abstract objective in measurable criteria. One or more problem statements are made to depict the existing dilemma, after which desired changes and also undesirable side effects are both defined as objectives, written as nouns. Connecting lines denote a defining relation. Each objective is defined by either none or more than one sub-objective, with the lowest objectives being operational^{lii}.

3.5 Mapping causal relations

Drawing from the means and criteria, the causal map depicts the effect of means and external factors on other factors and criteria. The map is elaborated by reasoning backwards from the criteria. At most twenty elements are included. Each causal relation is represented by an arrow, labelled with '+' for a positive relation, and '-' for a negative relation. Each factor is connected to at least one other factor. Any indirect path $X \rightarrow Y \rightarrow Z$ that also occurs with $X \rightarrow Z$ require an explanation of their different casual mechanisms, and underlying assumptions are documented^{liii}.

3.6 Constructing the system diagram

Combining the means, ends, and factors identified, the system diagram is formed. A dotted boundary is drawn to represent the system demarcation, along the top edge of which external factors are placed. The means are placed on the left, and the criteria on the right, leaving internal factors within the system boundary. Means and external factors do not receive incoming arrows, and external factors must have a route through to at least one criterion. Casual relationships identified are carried over, and all factors are noun phrases. This creates a conceptual model of the system that constitutes the problem for further analysis^{liv}.

3.7 Actor inventory

Actors who may exist in relation to the system diagram are identified through approaches such as interest, institution, and social participation. The highest possible level is selected for composite actors without losing information or irrelevant objectives. The list of actors, categorized by their roles and interests, is streamlined such that the interests and roles are balanced for the ten to twenty actors included^{lv}.

3.8 Formal relations map

The formal chart orients the positions of actors, creating a starting point to understand the playing field in which policy processes occur. It contextualizes informal relations and describes resource dependencies between actors. Key legislation and formal agreements are used as a starting point, and actors are positioned according to vertical hierarchy, shown by labelled arrows depicting influence. Clusters of actors are indicated with dotted rectangles^{lvi}.

3.9 Identifying actor characteristics

To map actors influence, their values, stances, and resources are identified through describing actor interests, objectives, and perceptions. Stable issues that matter the most to an actor with a clear direction are interests. Objectives describe what actors wish to achieve in the problem situation. Enserink et al. (2022) recommend what actors think to be the causes of and solutions to a problem should be identified. However, with the limited timeframe of the research, only the actors' possible perceptions are described based on secondary sources. Actor importance and the replaceability of their resources are identified to understand how much the problem owner depends on them^{lvii}.

3.10 Power-interest matrix

The power and interest held by actors identified are summarised and placed in the power-interest matrix. Actors who are both interested and hold power in the problem situation are key players who need to be managed closely. Actors who hold power but do not demonstrate interest are context setters to be handled with care. Interested actors with low power are subjects requiring some consideration, while disinterested actors with low power are part of the crowd to be monitored^{lviii}.

3.11 Limitations

Despite the replicable and explicit methodology, there are several limitations to stakeholder analysis. Hermans and Thissen (2009) have found that its analytic quality depends on scope, specificity, and logical interconnectedness. Stakeholder analysis is relatively low in analytic quality due to its "provisional" assessments of influence, but it can accommodate gaps in input data, is accessible, and allows the selection of appropriate items^{lix}. Less technical methods also offer less precision compared to those needing specialist computer software, so they may be acceptable often in rudimentary analyses^{lx}. In addition, hidden interests may skew the

analysis, and there exists the issue of research objectivity given the analysis is done from a particular perspective^{lxii}. Therefore, assumptions are explained as much as possible to make up for possible bias.

Due to the short timeframe of the research, policy documents, organization webpages, meeting minutes, and news reports were the main sources of information for document analysis. Key documents included the *City of Bath WHS Management Plan 2024-2030* providing the context of tourist taxes in Bath. However, participatory approaches such as interviews and surveys with stakeholders were not used, unlike that used by most literature. This limits the quality of data triangulation achievable through checking with key informants and regular peer review sessions^{lxiii}.

4 Results

4.1 Means-ends diagram

From the means-ends diagram constructed (Figure 2), the collection of tourist taxes is determined as the focal objective. The physical scope of the problem situation is restricted to the city of Bath, and the temporal demarcation assumes a point in time where various forms of tourist taxes are charged. It assumes that the UK government has permitted the implementation of tourist taxes by local authorities.

Figure 2. Means-ends diagram highlighting with a bolded border the collection of tourist taxes in the city of Bath as the focal objective.

The WHSEF was established in 2009 as a partnership between the WHS Advisory Board, BANES Council, and BPT, to organize minor enhancements, assist such projects, and arrange volunteers. It has so far participated in 50 schemes including the award-winning repairs to Bath’s incised and painted street signs^{lxiii}. The funding source comes from the Community Infrastructure Levy (CIL) and matched funding by BPT, while railing reinstatement around public areas is supported by Public Realm funding^{lxiv}.

There are alternate sources of income considered in the *Bath Public Realm and Movement Strategy*, including landowner investments, transport and funding bids, and BID schemes. Tourist tax as a source of funding appears to yet to be included^{lxv}. However, it is included in

the WHS management plan to explore options for a tourist tax, the revenue of which will be used for projects conserving the WHS OUV^{lxvi}.

4.2 Objectives tree

Based on the focal objective of 'increased tourist tax council income', criteria related to increased council investment in the public realm are derived. Public transport income (£/annum) is used as a criterion by proxy indicating an increased number of tourists. However, there are also frequent visitors arriving to Bath for reasons such as work. These are linked in the objectives tree (Figure 3).

The council also operates major tourist attractions in Bath through its Heritage Services^{lxvii}. Therefore, increased tourist visits to council-owned venues can contribute to its income. However, venue income can also occur through venue hires, so that increased visitors over time is also included as one of the criteria.

Increased tourist accommodation bookings is used as a criteria by proxy indicating more overnight tax collected. This is indicated by increased bookings over time in Bath which contribute to levy collected from tourist accommodation, and simply income over time from overnight stay tax collected directly. These criteria are based on different models of tax collection, such that they are considered separately.

Accommodation tax itself alone can be considered in many forms, and one of the ways not considered yet is the charging of licensing fees from private AirBNBs^{lxviii}. The feasibility of different tourist tax models in Bath is beyond the scope of this work and should be considered in a separate study.

Council spending on public realm is considered separately to tourist arrivals in Bath, as it occurs consequentially to increased council income from tourist tax collected. The criteria is based on the *Bath Pattern Book's* aspiration for increased stone paving as one of the measures to restore the public realm as intended^{lxix}. As the restoration requires significant investment, an increased budget allocation would also create one of the criteria for increased council spending on the public realm.

The BANES Council *Public Realm and Movement Strategy* proposes three stages of projects that deliver its strategy, including early win projects tackling issues of immediate concern, preparatory projects delivering public realm products, and transforming spaces projects delivering major capital works incrementally transforming streets and public spaces^{lxx}. Increased funding from tourist tax would enable more of these projects to be carried out.

4.3 Causal relations map

Based on the criteria developed, the causal relations map (Figure 4) shows the relationships between mutable factors. These are based on the *Movement Strategy* and WHS Advisory Board meetings where the Federation of Bath's Residents' Associations (FoBRA) expressed dissatisfaction with the state of the public realm^{lxxi}, so an improved public realm likely leads to a positive increase in residents' quality of life. It is also assumed that increased outdoor space for city centre establishments is likely to increase local business income and strengthen its economy, as the quality and vibrancy of streets influence how businesses feel about Bath^{lxxii}.

Figure 3. Objectives tree showing the fundamental means to achieving the focal objective of increased tourist tax.

Figure 4. Causal relations map showing positive and negative causations between means, factors, and criteria.

There are two causal loops identified in this extracted part of the causal relations map (Figure 5). An improved public realm improves the business capacity of establishments and is expected to attract more tourists. However, the implementation of arrivals tax increases the cost of visiting Bath and may negatively impact the number of tourists visiting Bath. As there are more positive relations than negative relations in this set of loops, it is expected that investing in the public realm is likely to improve tourist visitation than deter it even with an increased cost. This assumes investment in the public realm improves business prospects in the city centre (see Figure 5 (a)).

Figure 5. Extracted part of causal relations map (a) and (b).

There is also more than one causal path leading to council income in this extracted part of the causal relations map (see Figure 5 (b)). The more tourist tax collected through various models

of tourist taxes; the more council income can be reinvested in the public realm. However, more transport use increases emergency public realm projects needed to maintain wear and tear. If both influences are just equally strong, the implementation of tourist tax will be largely spent on maintenance works instead of projects which further the council's vision for Bath's public realm. For a net improvement in public realm, transport use on roads needs to be regulated and reorganised. This is evidenced in the council's inclusion of proposed actions in The Joint Local Transport Plan for the West of England prioritising pedestrians, cyclists, and public transport^{lxxiii}.

4.4 System diagram

The system diagram summarizes the findings from the means-ends analysis, objectives tree, and causal analysis. Only arrivals tax and accommodation tax are included, so that this is a subsystem diagram illustrating the impact on criteria quantifying works to Bath's public realm (see Figure 6).

It can be seen from the diagram that an increase in budget allocated is the key criterion that enables more public realm projects and increases the area of natural stone paving. This is traced to the increase in council income from charging arrivals and accommodation tax, which is in a causal loop. More tourists are attracted by an improved public realm, but they can also be deterred from the increased cost of visiting Bath. This is largely dependent on UK legislation as an external factor, which enables the implementation of tourist taxes. Climate change is another external factor that not only impacts the condition of the public realm and what is designed to accommodate potential threats, but also tourism^{lxxiv}.

From tracing the system diagram, the key internal factor is the number of tourists visiting Bath, as it is connected to the greatest number of causal arrows. Tourists affect the public realm condition, as the use of transport causes wear and tear on road conditions. The more tourists there are visiting Bath, the more income there is to the council to reinvest into the public realm. However, both a decline in the public realm condition and an increased cost of visiting Bath may deter tourists.

As shown by the consequences table connecting means and criteria (Table 1), charging arrivals tax has a straightforward positive relationship with budget allocated towards conservation, as it increases council income. However, it raises the cost of visiting Bath, which has the potential to deter tourists using transport. Should the tax decrease the number of tourists, there will be less wear and tear on the public realm from transport use, thus preserving existing areas of natural stone paving and allowing public realm projects in new areas. This criterion will rely on other sources of funding should taxes be insufficient. Charging accommodation tax also has a similar causal path to charging arrivals tax, where more income leads to an increased budget allocated towards conservation.

The consequences table below maps causal relationships between external factors and criteria (Table 2). Assuming UK legislation supports the implementation of tourist taxes by local authorities, the enablement of tourist taxes is likely to contribute positively to the criteria as demonstrated in the means-criteria consequences table. However, if tourist taxes continue being blocked by the UK government, it becomes even more necessary to manage traffic and seek alternative funding sources, both of which are accounted for in the *Movement Strategy*^{lxxv}.

Figure 6. Sub-system diagram with means on the left, criteria on the right, and external factors on top of the system boundaries.

Table 1. Consequences table tabulating positive and negative causal relationships between means and criteria.

		Criteria		
		Area of natural stone paving	Frequency of new public realm projects	Budget allocated towards conservation
Means	Charge arrivals tax	+/-+/-/-	+/-+/-/+	+/+/+
	Charge accommodation tax	+/-+/-/-	+/-+/-/+	+/+/+

Table 2. Consequences table tabulating positive and negative causal relationships between external factors and criteria.

		Criteria		
		Area of natural stone paving	Frequency of new public realm projects	Budget allocated towards conservation
External factors	UK Legislation	+/+/-+/-/+	+/+/-+/-/+	+/+/+
	Traffic management	-/+/+	-/+	+
	Climate change	-/+	-/+	+
	Other funding sources	+/+	+/+	+

Climate change is another external factor which may impact the condition of the public realm, as the effects of climate change are unpredictable and may negatively impact both historic and contemporary elements. However, this is likely to be accounted for in new designs for the public realm, where increasing water absorption rates of street surfacing will be considered, in order to deal with increased rainfall^{lxxvi}. Climate change also may impact upon whether tourist visits to Bath due to increased adverse weather conditions. This external factor is accounted for and discussed by the WHS Advisory Board^{lxxvii}.

The external factor of other funding sources as proposed by the *Movement Strategy* directly contributes to the area of natural stone paving that can be produced and conserved, as the result of new public realm projects. The causal path does not pass through the factor of tourist numbers visiting Bath, meaning tourists lack direct influence. However, the improved public realm condition is likely to increase tourist numbers in Bath. Should tourist taxes remain blocked by UK legislation, there are other means and factors which may positively contribute to conservation ambitions and the public realm of Bath.

4.5 Actor inventory

Fifteen actors are identified through the approaches described. Interest-based actors include the Mayors' coalition, UK Hospitality, European Tourism Association (ETOA), and Bath Preservation Trust (BPT), that are political lobbying groups interested in acting upon issues of tourist tax or conservation in Bath. Institutional actors concerned with WHS conservation include ICOMOS, WH Centre, Department for Culture, Media, and Sport (DCMS), Historic England (HE), Bath WHS Advisory Board, and BANES Council, while His Majesty's (HM) Treasury is concerned with UK tax policy, and Visit West is concerned with promoting tourism in Bath. Actors identified through the social participation approach include Bath residents, Bath BID, and tourists who are likely to express their opinions through representative groups. Actor demographics are currently focused on Bath residents as there are no known demographical impacts.

The BANES Council is a composite actor and are identified as a singular actor in relation to other actors, in addition, the DCMS, HM Treasury, and Secretary of Ministry of Housing, Communities, and Local Government (MHCLG) are part of the UK Government. However, they

are national level actors with different interests and responsibilities, so they are listed separately. An omitted actor is the recently established All-Party Parliamentary Group (APPG) on UNESCO WHS. As the APPG seeks to grow support and share good practice of WHS management, it currently appears unlikely the APPG will be an active actor in the Bath tourist tax problem situation^{lxviii}. The identified actors are sorted at interest-based levels (Figure 7) and at decision-making levels (Figure 8).

Figure 7. Actors sorted by interests – conservation, governance, living, and tourism.

Figure 8. Actors sorted by levels from international to individual.

4.6 Formal chart

The formal chart (Figure 9) shows the formal relationships between stakeholders identified from the actor inventory. The WH Committee is placed at the top of the hierarchy as it authorizes the WH List and decides sites to be included or excluded^{lxxxix}. The WH Centre is the focal point and coordinator within UNESCO for WH matters, collaborating with State Parties and Advisory Bodies to act as the main hub of communication in UNESCO with the State Party regarding impacts on WHS OUV^{lxxx}.

The UK ratified the UNESCO WH Convention in 1984, with the DCMS undertaking responsibility of the State Party, while also being the lead department for national policy regarding WH. Under the Levelling Up and Regeneration Act 2023, WHS are designated heritage assets, and the National Planning Policy Framework (NPPF) places them of the highest significance under Paragraphs 195 and 206b, such that they receive the greatest weight in conserving their significance^{lxxxix}. The DCMS also engages across UK government departments on WH matters, including the Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO), the MHCLG, and the Department for Environment, Food, and Rural Affairs (DEFRA)^{lxxxii}. However, these departments are not involved with matters related to hospitality and tourism, thus existing beyond the system boundaries and not included in the formal chart.

HE acts as the government’s heritage advisor and is a statutory part of the planning process. Being an executive non-departmental public body, it is sponsored by the DCMS^{lxxxiii}. It engages with UNESCO and the WH Centre on new or revised policies and reporting processes, while advising the UK State Parties, owners, decision-makers, and communities on technical matters and proposed changes to WHS^{lxxxiv}.

Figure 9. Formal chart of actors identified showing formal relationships between tax, conservation, and tourism-interested actors.

Reporting and monitoring occur between the WH Committee and State Party. Under paragraph 172 of the *Operational Guidelines for the Implementation of the WH Convention*, the WH Committee is informed, through the Secretariat of the UK, the state party's decision to allow major developments affecting a WHS OUV, helping the committee seek its full preservation. The DCMS has the ultimate say on whether the case will be notified to the WH Committee with advice from HE. Under paragraph 174, the WH Centre may receive information regarding a WHS from a source other than the State Party if there are issues about its state of conservation. This information will be verified with the State Party who responds under liaison with the national heritage agencies^{lxxxv}. ICOMOS acts as an advisory body to the WH Centre, as named within the WH Convention, making it also an official advisor of state parties^{lxxxvi}. ICOMOS-UK advises on aspects of WHS for nomination and promotes best practice in conserving the historic environment^{lxxxvii}.

The HM Treasury is the economic and finance ministry of the UK government. It sets most taxes in the country, making England an exception where little taxation is set by or assigned to local authorities^{lxxxviii}. It holds decisive power over tax policies, and recently blocked the Secretary of Ministry of Housing, Communities, and Local Government (MHCLG), Angela Rayner, from devolving tourist taxes to local authorities in her recent white paper^{lxxxix}. The opinions of HM Treasury officials reflect that of groups, such as UK Hospitality, who lobby in favour of the hospitality sector^{xc}. The European Tourism Association (ETOA) is an organization that similarly lobbies for fair tourist taxes across the region^{xc}. The mayors' coalition, including

those of the Liverpool City Region, Greater Manchester, and London, are instead lobbying for tourist tax powers, having signed a joint letter in June 2025^{xcii}.

The BANES council is one of the local authorities interested in implementing tourist taxes. As the principal coordinator of WH, it employs the WHS manager, who implements the WHS Management Plan and is overseen by the Bath WHS Advisory Board. Stakeholders represented on the WHS Board include HE, BANES Council, DCMS, ICOMOS UK, Federation of Bath Residents’ Associations (FoBRA), and BPT^{xciii}. The BANES Council also partially funds Visit West, the Local Visitor Economy Partnership (LVEPs) representing Bristol, BANES, North Somerset, and South Gloucestershire^{xciv}, which supports collaborative growth of the local visitor economy. Local lobbying groups include the Bath BID, which is led by and lobbies in favour of Bath businesses^{xcv}, and BPT which lobbies in favour of quality public realm treatment and conservation initiatives^{xcvi}.

As seen from the formal chart, the BANES Council is subject to monitoring and legislative controls from the UK Government, while being responsible to local lobbying groups, residents, and tourists – all of whom hold conflicting opinions on the issue of tourist taxes.

4.7 Actor overview table

The actor overview (Table 3) shows support of implementing tourist tax from actors in conservation and those who wish for a better quality of life, such as some Bath residents. However, stakeholders who generate income from tourism, including other Bath residents, are less likely to support the implementation of tourist tax, as shown in literature^{xcvii} and local news^{xcviii}. On the other hand, the council anticipates a younger tourist demographic and a shift towards a creative, wellbeing-based economy through the creation of a high-quality public realm^{xcix}. There is some divergence in what is desired by local businesses and the long-term economic strategy by the council.

Table 3. Stakeholder inventory table identifying interests, objectives, perceptions, resources, and their dependency.

Stakeholder	Interests	Objectives	Perceptions	Resources	Importance	Replaceability	Dependency
WH Committee	Implement the World Heritage Convention and determine inscription of sites	Maintenance of OUV at WHS globally	WHS status is administered at the supra-national level and is not embedded in local legislation, so there is little control over nations	Decisive authority over WHS Supra-national position Significant media platform	Yes	No	High
ICOMOS	Evaluate WHS for their eligibility to remain on the WHL	Advise World Heritage Committee and state parties on nominations, management, and conservation (ICOMOS, n.d.)	Advise on Bath WHS Management plan (Bath WHS Manager, 2025, 38)	Information of WHS worldwide Skilled manpower in evaluating WHS and researching heritage themes (ICOMOS, 2025)	Yes	No	High
EOTA	Lobby and participate in expert groups on	Establishment of tax framework on which	Any increase in industry's cost without	Lobbying power for fair tourist taxes	No	No	Medium

	legislative review; Provide expert advice; and Produce research and report on policy impact Monitor places with destination taxes (ETOA, 2025b)	reciprocal paying services support purposes benefitting residents, and easy to comply with (ETOA, 2025b)	i.e. reciprocal for or competiveness (ETOA, 2019, 3)	reciprocal benefit is demanded by competitiveness (ETOA, 2019, 3)	Quantitative information on tourism Skilled research manpower on tourism Organisation of developing constructive relationships with destinations and local stakeholders (ETOA, 2025a)			
HM Treasury	Strategic oversight of UK tax system (HM Treasury, n.d.)	Sustainable economic growth Simple and fair taxing (HM Treasury, n.d.)	Reject proposals for local taxes as existing VAT is already high (Wilson, 2025)	Authority over UK taxes Knowledge of UK economy – National Visitor Economy Strategy pending publication	Yes	No	High	
DCMS	Responsibility for WH matters in the UK, and support creative industries and tourism across England (gov.uk, n.d.)	Establish Visitor Economy Advisory Council to co-create visitor economy growth strategy and advise on any tourist tax proposals (UK Parliament, 2025); enforce conservation legislation through the English planning system	Pay extra attention to developments which may affect Bath's double-inscribed OUV (Bath WHS Manager, 2025, 38)	Legal authority over UK WHS and conservation	Yes	No	High	
HE	Strategic involvement in planning and development ; Advise DCMS on implementing the 1972 WHS convention in the UK (Historic England, 2025c)	Maintenance of OUV in English WHS through the planning system (Historic England, 2025a)	Develop and provide guidance managing WHS in England (Historic England, 2025a)	Knowledge of UK WHS and professional conservation and archaeology knowledge Skilled manpower – conservation advisers Authority on UK conservation Knowledge of public realm works in historic	Yes	No	High	

					environment (Historic England, 2018)			
UK Hospitality	Represent UK hospitality sector policy lobbying (UK Hospitality, 2024)	Ensured continued success of hospitality and tourism sector	Tourist incurs compliance burden and reduces tourist spending due to high existing VAT (Nicholls, 2025)	tax Information of the UK hospitality sector Representativ e position of hospitality sector Organisation for lobbying Own media platforms (website, social media)	No	No	Medium	
Mayors' coalition	Lobbying for local authorities of cities to have the power to implement overnight stay tourist tax (Al- Othman, 2025)	Implementatio n of tourist tax benefitting the maintenance of respective cities and tourism as a result	Politicization of tourist tax prolongs formation of legislation	tax Information of UK cities involved Representativ e position of major UK cities Organisation of mayors for lobbying Access to news media platforms	No	Yes	Low	
Visit West	Develop, manage, and market the visitor economy for local authorities and private sector within the West of England (Visit West, 2025a)	Achieve recognition as an exemplar LVEP by developing an innovative and sustainable visitor economy (Visit West, 2025a)	Report on tourist tax developments in the West of England region (Visit West, 2025c)	tax Organisation of local authorities and private sectors in West of England Skilled manpower to support growth of private companies (Visit West, 2025b)	No	Yes	Low	
BANES Council	Partly support WHSEF (BPT, n.d.) Acquire Public Realm Funding to support conservation of historic objects; Accommodat e stakeholder opinions and make balanced judgements	20-year strategic improvement of Bath public realm to develop a higher quality visitor economy (BANES Council, 2023, 18) Collect tourist tax to supplement financial funding for public realm improvement	Difficulty of implementing tax due to political restrictions; Unanimously supports principle of tourist tax in Bath (Wimperis, 2025); Sign joint letter with Cambridge appealing for tourist taxes (Tegg, 2025)	Council income Formal power as local authority Knowledge of area of Bath Organisation for conservation projects and consultations Own media platform (website) and access to news media platforms	Yes	No	High	

Bath BID	Champion interests of Bath businesses, reduce overheads, and improve business environment (Bath BID, 2021, 6)	(Greenwood, 2025) Improve public realm and user experience in the district (Bath BID, 2021, 11)	Likely perceive Bath status as a planning constraint (WHS Advisory Board, 2022); possibly willing to put up with tourists who contribute to business revenue (Fair, 2025)	Income from levy collected Knowledge of tourism statistics Organisation for street deep cleaning, preventing antisocial behaviour, and business network	No	Yes	Low
BPT	Apply pressure to ensure heritage conservation in Bath Match fund Bath WHSEF	Maintain authenticity of Bath as a city including the protection of its OUV	Support robust and compliant streetscape maintenance strategy city-wide (BPT, 2022) Establish principles and suggestions for Bath's public realm (BPT, 2025)	Knowledge of the heritage values of Bath Income from charity business operations Organisation al power of conservation professionals in Bath	Yes	No	High
Bath residents	Conservation of historic sites in Bath; good quality of life	Pride of place from living in a UNESCO inscribed historic city	Debris and damage to public realm from business and tourism	Some lobbying power through FoBRA Reporting power through BANES Council and BPT (BANES Council, 2025a; BPT, n.d.) Some organisational power through interpersonal networks Personal media platforms	No	No	Medium
Tourists	Visit Bath and enjoy its heritage setting at an acceptable cost	Bath existing as a thriving historic city (WHS Advisory Board, 2020)	Possible deterrence from visiting due to both increased cost and damage to public realm	Spending power for council and businesses' incomes Personal media platforms reflecting personal experience	No	Yes	Low

Important stakeholders have significant decision-making power in the WHS status of Bath or policies related to tourist tax. Political lobbying groups are less important and are replaceable. Conservation-interested actors have lobbying power on conservation related issues but less so on tourist taxation. Individual-level actors such as Bath residents and tourists have the least decision-making tools in the set of actors but cannot be replaced.

Though multiple stakeholders share interests in conservation, there is little overlap with the power to implement tourist tax as much as there is interest in its principle. In addition, there are lobbying groups for hospitality and tourism that are more interested in economic success than conservation. There is a noticeable gap between those interested in conservation and that of tourist tax, where conservation actors are interested in implementation, but those who are opposed to implementing tourist taxes may not be as interested in or knowledgeable about the investment needs of the public realm.

4.8 Power-interest matrix

Based on the actor dependencies, they are placed into the power-interest matrix (Figure 10). Actors who hold decisive enabling or blocking power over tourist taxes and conservation are placed according to increasing power, and those with a strong interest in conservation are placed according to increasing interest, thus mapping the stakeholders.

Figure 10. Power-interest matrix of involved stakeholders in the tourist tax problem situation.

Of the six problem-contexts identified by Jackson (2004), the tourist tax dilemma may be identified as systemic-pluralistic. ‘Systemic’ problem-contexts contain complex systems that produce difficult problems, and ‘pluralist’ participants hold different objectives, but they may achieve a compromise. For this, soft systems thinking is recommended to tackle the lack of agreement about objectives and difficulties. However, the local authority-government relationship expresses some elements of coercive-systemic problem contexts, where consensus over the passing of a tourist tax bill is subject to the domination of HM Treasury over other stakeholders. Unfortunately, there has yet to be literature addressing the resolution of these problem situations. Despite this, it is possible to influence context setters

to move towards becoming key players through political lobbying. The effort may take time, but it is already ongoing^{cii}.

Key players include the BANES Council, DCMS, HE, and the WHS Advisory Board. These are actors who are highly interested in conservation and hold influential or decisive power on the WHS status of Bath and conservation issues. However, these are not actors who may directly enable tourist taxes. The HM Treasury and the Secretary of MHCLG are placed in the category of context setters, with high power but low interest in conservation matters. Despite being context setters, they hold conflicting opinions on allowing local authorities the power to implement tourist taxes, with the HM Treasury exhibiting blocking power when passing legislative bills on the matter^{ciii}. These are actors that need to be satisfied and handled with care. However, as they hold authority over the BANES council, it is difficult to do so.

Garnering support from lobbying groups who are in favour of tourist taxes may support the BANES Council in appealing to context setters with blocking power. They include the mayors' coalition, who is placed in the crowd category. Although the mayors' coalition may just be monitored, working with the coalition may lend strength to lobbying for the power to implement tourist taxes. However, lobbying groups who may oppose the implantation of tourist taxes are also in the crowd category. These are stakeholders who hold their own agendas and thus have less interest in tourist taxes for conservation. However, they still have the resources to voice opposition against tourist taxes, especially those in the hospitality and business sector.

Although tourist taxes have been shown to have variable and even beneficial effects on the hospitality sector, collaboration and negotiation is needed to achieve a mutually beneficial agreement. Buckley (2018) recommends criteria to select appropriate private applicants to partner with heritage agencies: respect for the agency's authority over the WHS, reciprocity between both parties, a good track record of partnership with heritage agencies, and appropriate business expertise^{civ}. As it remains difficult to create strong influence on the UK government to enable local tourist taxes, the next best option is to adopt the tourist tax model of Manchester^{cv} and establish an accommodation BID for the collection of tourist taxes. However, the council-established tax model differs from that of the industry-backed tax model, so addressing the concerns of and achieving consensus with the local hospitality sector is recommended. Care should also be taken in maintaining trust with tourism providers^{cv}, so that collaboration attempts would remain viable and sustainable.

Tourists visiting Bath are placed in the subject category, as they are likely interested in the destination being a heritage city and maintaining its tourism value. However, they may not have as much power when subjected to tourist taxes, other than choosing to not visit Bath out of increased cost concerns. Buckley (2018) has also found little evidence that tourists become effective advocates for conservation after visiting WHS, as they consider themselves on holiday, so changed attitudes may not produce a net contribution in favour of conservation^{cvi}. Though Buckley looked at the case of environmental conservation, it is possible similar applies to historic conservation and tourism. Although similar studies can provide reference, conducting a tourist-specific survey of their willingness to pay and conservation awareness may facilitate the decision of acceptable tourist tax models.

Bath residents are placed in the centre of the power-interest matrix, as they hold the most variable interest and mutable power in the problem situation. They may build alliances among themselves to lobby for or against tourist taxes. Soares et al. (2022) identified different clusters of residents grouped by perception of tourist taxes at a WHS, and it is possible that similar opinion categories exist among Bath residents^{cvi}. Some Bath residents may seek a better quality of life and agree with the use of tourist taxes for reinvestment in the public realm and control tourist flows. However, other Bath residents may value the revenue brought by tourism

– whether they work in the hospitality sector – and choose to tolerate its detrimental effects^{cxix}. Further research is needed to understand resident perceptions and the measured impact of tourist taxes on residents' quality of life.

Despite divergent opinions among stakeholders, relationships are relatively balanced compared to case studies reviewed^{cx}. The creation of the WHS management plan has involved a rigorous participatory process that included key stakeholders over a period of two years and the local community during an 8-week public consultation^{cxii}. In addition, there has been interest and policies in engaging local businesses and residents to raise awareness on the WH significance of Bath^{cxiii}. There is basis for strong relationships at a local level for the implementation of tourist taxes, which may be strengthened by working across lobbying groups and local authorities to appeal for devolved tourist tax powers.

4.9 Areas for further research

This research also contributes to stakeholder analysis in the area of heritage, to the author's knowledge being the first to use the methodology to examine tourist taxes. The literature review provides an overview of the tourism-heritage conflict, stakeholder analysis in heritage, and the politics of tourism taxes. By using an accessible form of stakeholder analysis, it contributes to the industry understanding of stakeholder relationships that may occur in similar political dilemmas.

The system diagram could be improved and stakeholder analysis revisited with a further added participatory process involving representative stakeholders – likely the WHS Advisory Board – in giving their expert opinion on the problem situation. Reed et al. (2009) identified that participatory approaches to stakeholder analysis require the involvement of stakeholders in identifying foci and boundaries, so an iterative approach between system demarcation and stakeholder method applications is needed to continuously refine problem construction and lead to strategies representative of stakeholders^{cxiii}. Participatory approaches used in literature for stakeholder analysis include expert evaluation^{cxiv}, researcher participation in stakeholder meetings^{cxv}, and semi-structured interviews^{cxvi}. However, the collection of actor perceptions from interviews can be time and financially consuming and may be an item of consideration for future research^{cxvii}.

To further understanding of the problem situation, directions for future research include semi-structured interviews with members of the Bath WHS Advisory Board to understand their expert experience of tourism taxes and resident surveys to gain a comprehensive understanding of resident perceptions and their positions in the power-interest matrix. Tourists may also be surveyed to gauge their willingness to pay and awareness of heritage conservation in Bath, and semi-structured interviews with the hospitality sector in Bath may be used to understand potential concerns about tourist taxes.

As shown in the literature review, stakeholder analysis is one of the ways to structure problem situations in a systematic manner. This may be combined as part of MCDA or mixed-methodology approaches to facilitate decision making, providing a starting point to achieve a structured understanding of stakeholder dynamics in implementing tourist taxes in Bath. A potential next step may be to construct stakeholder influence diagram indicating the influence of stakeholders on power-interest grid on each other, then carry out a centrality analysis to identify actors central to the network through a scoring system to identify who and how change may be enacted^{cxviii}. This helps to seek supra-interests that garner support from a significant number of stakeholders, consequently finding a common good to create persuasive arguments for.

5 Conclusion

The article has used the potential implementation of tourist taxes in Bath for conservation as a case study to analyse stakeholders in a heritage problem situation. The literature review examines the tourism-heritage relationship, the theoretical background to stakeholder analysis for decision-making and power dynamics, and the applications of tourist taxes internationally and in the UK. The methodology introduces the research method developed by Enserink et al., (2022), the problem context, and limitations associated with the method. The results present the problem structuring and stakeholder diagrams along with discussions of its assumptions and implications.

The system diagram and consequences table identify that even though 'tourists visiting Bath' is a crucial internal factor, external factors such as 'alternative sources of funding' can still help realize the public realm strategy and traffic management is needed to control the deterioration of the public realm^{cxix}. Climate change may cause uncontrolled detriment to the public realm, but the most significant external factor is UK legislation. This is similarly reflected in the stakeholder analysis, with the HM Treasury presenting authority over the BANES council. Establishing a BID is a feasible alternative to implementing tourist taxes, however, they require collaboration and the development of trust with stakeholders, including lobbying parties, businesses, residents, and tourists.

This work mainly contributes to exploring options for tourist taxes to manage tourism and improve the public realm. The system diagram and stakeholder matrix offer a systematic overview of the problem situation and likely relevant stakeholders involved, mapping the interaction of factors and relationships. This produces a rudimentary starting point from which to proceed in more specific consultation and collaboration directions.

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Annex A

Table 4. History of changes.

Version	Publication date	Change
1.0	31/10/2025	Initial version.

